

LIFESTYLE OF INDOOR SEED PLANTS AND ORIGIN

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Abstract: This article provides detailed information on the habitat and origin of angiosperms. In particular, information about the types, origin, way of life, spread on the earth and role in human life of closed seed plants is given.

Key words: angiosperms, autotrophic organisms, chloroplasts, species, photosynthesis, tissue, vegetative organs

Plants are the world of living organisms; autotrophic organisms with the ability to photosynthesize (see Autotrophs); the cell membrane usually consists of thick cellulose, the reserve nutrient is starch. Heterotrophic nutrition characteristic of some plants (saprophytes, parasites) is secondary. Other characteristics characteristic of plants (plants) (unique development cycle, the way organs are formed, clinging, etc.) are not common to all plants, but the set of these characters allows plants to be easily distinguished from other living organisms. Only at the lower level of structure, especially at the single-cell level, the difference between plants and other organisms is not so clearly felt; therefore, zoologists include euglena-like algae as single-celled animals. The main difference between single-celled O. and other single-celled organisms is the presence of chloroplasts. As the level of structure increases, so does the difference between plants and other organisms.

As a result of adaptation of plants to absorb gaseous (photosynthesis) and liquid (water and mineral salts dissolved in it) substances from the environment in the process of nutrition, their body surface has become more and more enlarged. In higher plants, the expansion and specialization of the body surface led to the development of tissues and vegetative organs (see Tissue, Vegetative Organs). Many important features of the structure of plants are related to their growth and reproduction, as well as adaptation to distribution.

According to tradition, until the middle of the 20th century, all plants were divided into bottom plants (bacteria, algae, fungi, lichens) and higher plants (algae, psilophytes, plankton, arthropods, angiosperms, flowering plants). Today's bacteria

and fungi are separated into separate worlds. The plant world is divided into 3 sub-worlds: red algae and higher plants. These small worlds contain all of the 350,000 species of plants.

The origin of plants corresponds to the first development periods of life on earth. In this, organisms similar to blue-green algae (cyanobacteria) appeared in the Archaean era (3 billion years ago). True algae are thought to have appeared in the Proterozoic era, and green and red algae in the early Paleozoic. It is possible that the first high plants - rhyniophytes - originated at the border between Proterozoic and Paleozoic. They had rhizoids instead of roots. Arboreal woodpeckers originated in the Carboniferous; in the Permian they were replaced by the present-day cuttlefish. Coniferous plants appeared in the Carboniferous, and they were widespread in the Triassic and Jurassic periods. Flowering plants (angiosperms) appeared at the beginning of the Cretaceous period, and since then they have dominated Earth's flora. Plants are of great importance in the life of all living organisms on Earth. The life of animals and people cannot be imagined without plants. Plants with only green chlorophyll harvest sunlight energy by synthesizing organic compounds from inorganic substances; at the same time, plants take SO₂ gas from the atmosphere and release oxygen into the atmosphere, which is necessary for the respiration of almost all living organisms. In this way, green plants keep the composition of the atmosphere constant. Plants are the basis of the food chain as producers of organic matter.

Plants on Earth form various life forms (grasses, shrubs, trees, lianas, epiphytes, etc.). Phytocoenoses, consisting of different types of plants, determine the diversity of the Earth's landscape and other ecological conditions for organisms. Soil and peat are formed with the direct participation of plants. The formation of lignite and hard coal is also related to plants.

Among the diverse types of plants, seed plants, mainly flowering plants, are of great importance. Seed plants provide food, clothing, fuel, building materials, etc. (see Cultivated Plants). Man has learned to build artificial covers of cultural plants (arable fields, gardens, avenues, etc.) on very large areas, to create different varieties of O. However, over-harvesting of plants and unwise use of plant resources have led to their disappearance over large areas; there was a risk of complete disappearance of many plant species. For this reason, a special law was adopted in Uzbekistan on the protection of plants and the rational use of their natural resources (see: Nature protection). Rare and endangered plant species are included in the Red Book of Uzbekistan.

Currently, most of the plants that cover the Earth are angiosperms. Angiosperms are more complex than other groups of plants. They are flowering plants. A true flower does not occur in any of the plant groups except the angiosperms. A true flower is made up of pistil, pollinator and seed.

In angiosperms, the seed pod matures inside the nodule, surrounded by the wall of the nodule, instead of being exposed on the domed pips like in open-seeded plants. After pollination and fertilization, the seed pod becomes a seed and the nodule becomes a fruit. Hence, the seeds of angiosperms mature inside the fruit. That is why these plants are called angiosperms. Seedlings maturing in nodules and seeds developing in fruits are better protected from adverse environmental conditions: cold and excessive heat, drought and excessive humidity, pests and diseases.

One of the most important characteristics of this section is double fertilization. Angiosperms gradually began to dominate the plant world due to good, healthy seed development, quick and easy propagation, and rapid loss of growth characteristics.

Angiosperms (Angiospermae) are flowering plants - a division (type) of higher plants. Having a seed, double fertilization is its characteristic sign. The seed is located in the center of the flower and consists of a node, a column and a beak. A seed bud develops in the cavity of the seed node. A fertilized nodule develops into a fruit, and the seed pod inside it produces one or more seeds (hence the name). There are about 200,000 species and more than 10,000 genera belonging to 300 families. Although the classification began in the 16th century, a system accepted by science has not yet been developed. Dozens of systems have been proposed, two of which are the most widely accepted - the two-phase and one-phase systems. Many plants useful to humans, including food plants (flax, cotton, wheat, etc.), fodder plants (oats, alfalfa, etc.), aromatic, medicinal, fruit and rubber plants, belong to angiosperms. Building materials are obtained from some species.

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